

Quanta-yield and "Chemismus" in Light Reaction.¹

By J. PLOTNIKOW

Up to the present moment not a single case is known to us in which "non-absorbed" (*i.e.*, reflected or transmitted) light has been chemically active. Such a case is scarcely to be expected and therefore the photochemical absorption law of Grotthus-van't Hoff must be regarded as a fundamental law of photochemistry. Properly speaking it is only a special case of the general law of conservation of energy in so far as it here relates to the mutual action ("Wechselwirkung") between the chemical energy and the energy of radiation.

The amounts of substances photochemically transformed are proportional to the amounts of light absorbed and for the simplest case of a single photoactive component the equation of kinetic reaction in its differential form appears as

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = kA,$$

where M is the quantity of substance transformed (or formed), t the time, A the quantity of light absorbed, k the proportionality factor which can also be regarded as the velocity constant of the light-reaction. If we measure ΔM , the small amount of substance changed in the correspondingly small but still measureable interval of time Δt , the coefficient of utilisation—one can also call it the photochemical yield—can be calculated from the above formula as

$$K = \Delta M / \Delta t A.$$

We can measure this "utilisation coefficient" or yield, which represents the number of gram-molecules changed photochemically

¹ Translated by Dr. P. C. Mitter.

by the light energy absorbed per unit of time and per calorie (or erg), either by direct measurement of ΔM , Δt and A , or by measuring the light-reaction velocity constant with the help of the integrated kinetic equation. The first way is relatively simple and takes a short time while the second, on the other hand, is very complicated in every respect. In spite of this, one has to go the second way, as the first gives in the majority of cases values which have no real meaning. We shall explain this further. It is well known that the photochemical processes are of a very complicated character. They have very often a period of induction (see Curve 2, Fig. 1), are mostly accompanied by all sorts of dark-reactions (Curve 4), possess often an autocatalytic character (Curve 3), form substances which absorb thermally, *i.e.*, extinguish the chemically acting light and are subject to complicated light partition between several components (Plotnikow and Weber, *Z Elektrochem.*, 1928, 34, 316), or the reaction tends to an equilibrium, that is, a reverse reaction with its photoactive components opposes it and diminishes the velocity of the first, etc., etc. In many cases, several of the phenomena related above, occur simultaneously. All these distort the normal course of a light-reaction as can be seen distinctly from Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

The determination of ΔM in the interval of time Δt does not, therefore, in these cases, correspond to the normal course of the reaction which is free from all sorts of disturbances. Unfortunately the estimations of the yields are made in most cases without taking these circumstances into consideration and they cannot therefore possess any real photochemical value. From this follows the conclusion that one must

first of all thoroughly investigate every reaction kinetically, measure all side reactions, subtract them from the total and measure the yield from the course of the pure light-reaction obtained in this manner. In this connection, particular attention is to be paid to the dark-reactions which are to be eliminated according to the author's addition principle.

Let us assume that we have succeeded in freeing a light-reaction from all side reactions or in eliminating them by calculation, and arrived in this way at the course of the pure light-reaction. What should we do next? It is clear that we must determine the change of the light-reaction velocity constant with the wave-length as we shall have to deal mostly with complex absorption relations. Were these so simple that we had to deal only with strips of photochemical absorption, as for instance in the case of the bleaching of colouring matters thoroughly investigated photochemically by Lasareff (*Ann. Physik*, 1907 **24**, 661) and Zschodro (*J. Chim. Phys.*, 1929, **16**, 59), the reaction velocity would then be independent of the wave-length, because the velocity depends only on the absorbed light energy. Ordinarily, however, thermic absorption is associated with the photochemical absorption, giving the total absorption processes a very complicated form. Fig. 2 is a symbolic representation of these relations. The strips of photochemical absorption possess, as the experiments have shown (Plotnikow and Karshulin, *Z. Physik*, 1926, **36**, 271), mostly a very simple form with a single maximum. The possibility of occurrence of a number of maxima by the superposition of several strips of photochemical absorption is, however, not excluded. In these whole strips, the velocity is proportional to the energy absorbed and the proportionality coefficient is independent of the wave-length. But as we measure in practice not the photochemical but the total absorption, so, the proportionality coefficient must accordingly change with the wave-length.

If we succeed in measuring K for the pure photochemical absorption for any particular wave-length, we can, with the help of this value of K and the constant k_λ for any other wave-length λ for which the total absorption $c_\lambda = A_\lambda + B_\lambda$) calculate the photochemical absorption A_λ corresponding to this wave-length according to the

equation $A = \frac{k_\lambda}{K} C_\lambda$. For this wave-length λ , the velocity $\frac{\Delta M_\lambda}{\Delta t} =$

$K_\lambda C_\lambda$, the chemical action is, however, effected only through the

photochemically absorbed light (see Fig. 2) so that we must have

$$\frac{\Delta M \lambda}{\Delta t} = \lambda K A.$$

Fig. 2.

The above given relation for $A\lambda$ is obtained for these two equations. In this way the curve of the entire photochemical absorption can be reconstructed and the absorption can be measured quantitatively even in case of complicated absorption processes. It is not excluded, however, that the same could be quantitatively measured by other methods, as for instance by applying a method similar to that of Henri, which was employed for measuring the light absorption constant with the help of the light absorptions spectra (Plotnikow and Karshulin, *loc. cit.*).

We can also put the calculation of the yield in quanta forms *i.e.*, measure the number of molecules changed photochemically for one light quantum absorbed. For this, one has to calculate $A : h\nu$, the number of quanta $h\nu$ present in the absorbed energy A and to measure the number of molecules transformed with the help of the Avogadro-Loschmidt constant. The quanta-yield becomes in this case

$$\psi = \frac{Q \Delta M}{q \Delta t}$$

where Q is the Avogadro-Loschmidt number and q the number of absorbed light-quanta ($= A/h\nu$). The calculation of ψ can be further simplified if we take the ratio of gram-molecules transformed to the gram-molecules light-quanta $Qh\nu$ absorbed, as we can measure the change in gram-molecules (ΔM) directly and calculate $Qh\nu$ from the photochemical tables of my book ("Photo-Chemische Versuchstechnik," 2nd Edition, 1928, pp. 327, 359).

As is well-known $Q = 6.06 \times 10^{23}$ and $h = 6.56 \times 10^{-27}$ erg. sec., and the frequency ν has been calculated in the tables for every wave-

length. On dividing the values given there for $\nu \times 10^{12}$ by 10, one obtains the gram-molecular light-quanta energy in big calories (*loc. cit.*).

Let us assume that we have before us only photochemical absorption that is only the inner curve in Fig. 2 as is for instance the case in the experiments of Lasareff and Zschodro. The yield measured in terms of energy remain constant, independent of the wave-length. Not, however, the quanta yields because, for example, they must be different in two equal absorptions a_1 and a_2 , as ν increases and thereby the value of ψ decreases. How is it then that by a different method of calculation one arrives at such an abnormal end-result? It is clear that this disagreement is due to some tacit assumption which is contradictory to the real facts. The assumption is that a light-quantum brings about the change only of a single molecule and that thereby the quantum transforms its energy completely into chemical energy. Both the assumptions which have hitherto been regarded as something axiomatic cannot correspond to the real facts and that on the following grounds.

As is well known, an atom or a molecule represents a complex dynamic structure, consisting of numerous electrons rotating round the nucleus in different orbits. When a light quantum falls into this complex it must produce the most diverse effects such as one can represent symbolically by Fig. 3.

Fig 3

The energy $h\nu$ of the light-quantum can transform itself partly into heat radiation, kinetic energy of the molecules, (*i.e.*, heat) and chemical energy (case I). In case II, $h\nu$ would transform itself into

kinetic energy, heat radiation, chemical energy and fluorescence, i.e., again into radiation of lesser energy. In case III, $h\nu$ would be transformed into two new radiations $h\nu_1$, and $h\nu_2$ both with smaller frequencies but the sum $h\nu_1 + h\nu_2 = h\nu$, the so-called Raman-effect, would remain constant. In case IV (the so-called photoelectric effect) free electrons, pronounced fluorescence and chemical action would appear accompanied by weak heat-effect. In case V, principally free electrons are formed as is the case for instance with very hard Röntgen rays. These electrons can, in their turn, give rise to chemical action through electronic impact. Case IV corresponds to the ultra-violet portion of the spectrum. The case III, the Raman-effect, appears in all substances. The case II corresponds to the action of the rays with large wave-length and case I to the action of the infra-red rays. Of course many other possibilities of combination are conceivable. Besides a portion of the radiation is scattered in a diffused manner.

The percentage ratio of the different forms of light energy distribution depends not only on the reacting wave-length but also to a large extent on the "Chemismus" i.e., the chemical properties of each particular compound individually, the medium, the temperature, added catalysts and other active and inactive components. In very few exceptional cases, under quite definite conditions of experiment, can $h\nu$ be converted approximately completely in any one of the above given forms of energy. So, the method of representation of the primary stage of photochemical action as

which has become so common in recent times, has neither a real nor a symbolical significance. Also the enormous divergences which are obtained as the results of experiments with regard to the assumption, that an $h\nu$ is transformed completely into chemical energy, need not make us wonder. What strikes one is, on the other hand, the fact that no correct conclusions had been hitherto drawn from the results of these experiments (cf. *Physikal. Chem.* (Oxford band), 1929, 120; *Faraday Soc., Disc.*, 21, Part 3, p. 63; Bhattacharya and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 169 381; Plotnikow, *Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1922, 21, 134; 1923, 22, 108; *Phot. Korr.*, 1927, 63, 4; Plotnikow and Karschulin, *Z. Physik*, 1926, 36, 271; 1926, 38, 502; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1927, 33, 213).